

THE USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA FOR BUSINESS PURPOSES IN EUROPE

The indicator considers the percentage of companies that use at least two of the following social media: social networks, blogs and microblogs, knowledge sharing websites based on the Wikipedia model.

The variable is available in the period between 2016 and 2021 for DESI countries. The United Kingdom is not included among the countries analyzed by the indicator.

Ranking of countries by use of social media in 2021. Finland is in first place for the number of companies using social media with a value of 8.83%, followed by Ireland with an amount of 8.72 and Malta with a value of 8.65%. In the middle of the table there is Slovenia with a value of 4.77%, followed by Germany with a value of 4.58% and Croatia with a value of 4.47%. Hungary closes the ranking with a value of 2.35%, Bulgaria with an amount of 2.04% and Romania with an amount of 1.67%. Overall, on average, 5.1% of European businesses used social media systems in 2021.

Ranking of countries by percentage change in the use of social media between 2016 and 2021 in Europe. Finland is in first place by value of the percentage change in the use of social media between 2016 and 2021 with an amount equal to 107.37% equal to an amount of 4.58 units, followed by the Czech Republic with an amount of 98.46% equal to an amount of 2.202 units and from Luxembourg with an amount of 96.85% equal to an amount of 2.89 units. In the middle of the table there are Germany with an amount of 55.99% equal to an amount of 1.65 units, Croatia with an amount of 54.41% equal to an amount of 1.58 units, and Italy with a change of 53.72% equal to an amount of 1.52 units. Hungary closes the ranking with an amount of 3.53% equal to an amount of 0.080 units, Greece with a value of 2.615 equal to an amount of 0.097 units, and the Netherlands with an amount of -0.059% equal to a amount of -0.004 units.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with the k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. The following clusters are therefore identified:

- Cluster 1: Slovakia, Latvia, Estonia, Czech Republic, France, Portugal, Croatia, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Germany, Bulgaria, Romania, Slovenia, Greece, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Austria.
- Cluster 2: Cyprus, Ireland, Finland, Malta, the Netherlands, Denmark, Sweden, Spain, Belgium;

From the point of view of the analysis of the median value, it appears that the amount of the median value of C2 is equal to a value of 7.66 units while the value of C1 is equal to an amount of 3.96%. Therefore, the following ordering of the clusters derives: $C2 = 7.66 > C1 = 3.96$. From a geographical point of view, it appears that the countries of Northern Europe have a greater ability to use the tools of social media than the countries of Central and Southern Europe. This condition not only reflects a general setback in Southern Europe in the application of digital to business but also identifies a limitation for Southern European companies to make profits by exploiting the abundant opportunities offered by the internet and social media.

¹ Ph.D., Assistant Professor of Economics at Lum University Giuseppe Degennaro, and researcher in Economics at LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Statale 100 km 18, Bari, Puglia, Italy. Email: leogrande.cultore@lum.it

Network Analysis with the Manhattan Distance. Below is a network analysis carried out through the use of the Manhattan distance. In particular, 2 complex network structures and 2 simplified network structures were identified. In particular, there is a complex network structure consisting of Slovenia, Italy, Germany, Croatia, France, Slovakia. Particularly:

- Slovenia has a connection with Italy equal to an amount of 0.27 units and with Germany with a value equal to 0.27;
- Italy has a connection with Slovenia for a value equal to 0.27, with Germany with a value equal to 0.26, with France equal to an amount of 0.32 and with Croatia equal to an amount of 0.16 units;
- Germany has a connection with Slovenia equal to an amount of 0.27 units, and with Italy equal to an amount of 0.26 units, and with Croatia for an amount equal to 0.26;
- Croatia has a connection with Italy for a value of 0.16 units, with Germany for a value of 0.26 and with France with a value of 0.25 units;
- France has a connection with Italy equal to an amount of 0.32 units, with Croatia equal to an amount of 0.25 units and with Slovakia for an amount equal to 0.32;
- Slovakia has a connection with France for an amount of 0.32 units.

There is a complex network structure between Estonia, Latvia, and the Czech Republic. In particular:

- Estonia has a connection with Latvia equal to an amount of 0.27 units;
- Latvia has a connection with Estonia equal to an amount of 0.27 and with the Czech Republic for an amount equal to 0.097.
- The Czech Republic has a relationship with Latvia amounting to 0.097 units.

In addition, there are two simplified network structures as indicated below, namely:

- There is a two-way relationship between Austria and Luxembourg for an amount equal to 0.15;
- There is a two-way relationship between Bulgaria and Poland for an amount equal to 0.28 units.

Conclusions. The data show that the use of social media for business purposes in Europe grew by 5.11% between 2016 and 2021. However, entrepreneurs residing in Northern European countries are more able to use social media for business purposes. of business compared to the countries of Southern Europe. It should be considered that social media are very relevant for developing business activities because they allow, for example, to improve online sales through e-commerce, to optimize relationships in terms of customer relationship management-CRM and to increase the profits of the business by optimizing the opportunities offered by digitization. Therefore, it is precisely the countries of southern Europe, which are also the most backward from an economic point of view, those that would derive the greatest gains from the greater diffusion of social media in corporate business practices.

Declarations

Acknowledgment. I want to thank the colleagues of the Lum Enterprise S.r.l. and prof. Alberto Costantiello and Lucio Laureti of LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro.

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication and/or submission, and redundancies have been completely observed by the authors.

References

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2021). The Broadband Penetration in Europe. Available at SSRN 3953683.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The attractiveness of European research systems. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(10), 72-101.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The impact of R&D investments on corporate performance in European Countries. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(7), 186-201.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe, *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(11), 166-187.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2021). Human Resources in Europe. Estimation, Clusterization, Machine Learning and Prediction. (September 29, 2021). *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, e-ISSN.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., De Cristoforo, G., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The Innovation-Sales Growth Nexus in Europe. Available at SSRN 3933407.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2021). The Impact of Venture Capital Expenditures on Innovation in Europe. Available at SSRN 3930697.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2020). The Finance-Innovation Nexus in Europe. *IJSET-International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering & Technology*, 7(12).

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The Determinants of Human Resources in European Countries During the Period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(9), 145-171.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Employment in Innovative Enterprises in Europe. Available at SSRN.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The SMEs Innovation in Europe. Available at SSRN 3964059.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The Innovation-Friendly Environment in Europe. Available at SSRN 3933553.

Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., & Massaro, A. (2022). Fixed Broadband Take-Up in Europe. Available at SSRN 4034298.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Matarrese, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. Available at SSRN 3983218.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). The Determinants of Design Applications in Europe. Available at SSRN 3956853.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The Determinants of Innovation in European Countries in the period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(8), 91-126.

Leogrande, A., Birardi, G., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2019). Italian Universities: Institutional Mandate and Communitarian Engagement. *European Journal of Educational Management*, 2(2), 85-110.

Massaro, A., Magaletti, N., Giardinelli, V., Cosoli, G., Leogrande, A., & Cannone, F. (2022). Original Data Vs High Performance Augmented Data for ANN Prediction of Glycemic Status in Diabetes Patients. Available at SSRN 4082839.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Enterprises Providing ICT Training in Europe. Available at SSRN.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The Intellectual Assets in Europe. Available at SSRN 3956755.

Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., Giardinelli, V., & Massaro, A. (2022). The Determinants of Internet User Skills in Europe. Available at SSRN 4113155.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Foreign Doctorate Students in Europe. Available at SSRN 4032975.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). Estimation and Machine Learning Prediction of Imports of Goods in European Countries in the Period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, e-ISSN.

Costantiello, A., Leogrande, A., & Laureti, L. (2021). The corporate innovation in Europe. Available at SSRN 3964043.

Galiano, A., Leogrande, A., Massari, S. F., & Massaro, A. (2019). I processi automatici di decisione: profili critici sui modelli di analisi e impatti nella relazione con i diritti individuali. *Rivista italiana di informatica e diritto*, 1(2), 41-61.

Leogrande, A. (2022). Export of Medium and High-Tech Products in Europe (No. 112619). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Leogrande, A. (2022). Workers in the Knowledge Economy in Europe (No. 112538). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Leogrande, A. (2022). The Employment Impact of Innovation in Europe. University Library of Munich, Germany.

Massaro, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., Giardinelli, V., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Prediction of Diabetes. Available at SSRN 4135264.

Leogrande, A., Laureti, L., & Costantiello, A. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. Available at SSRN 4091597.

- Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., & Massaro, A. (2022). Broadband Price Index in Europe. Available at SSRN 4036690.
- Galiano, A., Leogrande, A., Massari, S. F., & Massaro, A. (2020). I dati non personali: la natura e il valore. *Rivista italiana di informatica e diritto*, 2(1), 61-77.
- Massaro, A., Costantiello, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., Giardinelli, V., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Fuzzy c-Means Clusterization and ANN-MLP Prediction of Malign Breast Cancer in a Cohort of Patients. Available at SSRN.
- Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., & Massaro, A. (2022). The Role of Broadband Price Index in Fostering Economic Growth and Digitization in Europe. *Journal of Human, Earth, and Future*, 3(1), 32-54.
- Massaro, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., Giardinelli, V., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Text Mining Approaches Oriented on Customer Care Efficiency. Available at SSRN.
- Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Marketing and Organizational Innovations in Europe. Available at SSRN 4186167.
- Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Determinants of Lifelong Learning in Europe. Available at SSRN.
- Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Matarrese, M. (2022). International Scientific Co-Publications in Europe. Available at SSRN 4117970.
- Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., Giardinelli, V., & Massaro, A. (2022). ICT Specialists in Europe. Available at SSRN.
- Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., & Massaro, A. (2022). e-Government in Europe. A Machine Learning Approach. (February 25, 2022).
- Massaro, A., Cosoli, G., Leogrande, A., & Magaletti, N. (2022). Predictive Maintenance and Engineered Processes in Mechatronic Industry: An Italian Case Study. *International Journal*, (1), 37-54.
- Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., Leogrande, A., & Massaro, A. (2022). Process Engineering and AI Sales Prediction: The Case Study of an Italian Small Textile Company. Available at SSRN 4026183.
- Leogrande, A. (2021). The Destruction of Price-Representativeness. Available at SSRN 3994021.
- Angelo Leogrande. (2022). SMEs SELLING ONLINE IN EUROPE. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7017850>
- Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Electronic Invoices in Europe. Il Sud Est. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7021412>
- Angelo Leogrande. (2022). IT FOR ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY IN EUROPE. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7023885>
- Angelo Leogrande. (2022). THE USE OF AI IN BUSINESSES IN EUROPE. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7023889>

